

Appendix – ELMTEX: Fine-Tuning Large Language Models for Structured Clinical Information Extraction. A Case Study on Clinical Reports*

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A Experiments

As depicted in Figure 1, the experiments in ELMTEX project explore three setups:

1. **Naive Prompting:** Directly querying the LLM with a simple instruction to extract information for all categories.
2. **Advanced Prompting with In-Context Learning:** Including examples of input-output pairs as context within the detailed prompt to guide the LLM.
3. **Fine-Tuning:** Training small LLMs on a domain-specific dataset for clinical reports. For this setup, the naive prompt was used.

A.1 Results on German Dataset

We present the results on the translated German dataset. Similarly to the English models, the fine-tuned models demonstrate the best performance. In particular, these models were trained just once using English and German data simultaneously. Despite this single training session, they outperform significantly larger models. Furthermore, we observe that all models perform worse in German than in English. This discrepancy is probably due to the limited pre-trained knowledge of German compared to English in the models.

B Dataset Example

Below is a JSON example from the English dataset. Within each category, extracted medical concepts are separated by semicolons (;). Categories that are not identified in the clinical report are noted with “N/A”. Due to its length, the patient’s clinical report has been truncated.

```
{
  "patient_id": "120212",
  "patient_uid": "5618395-1",
  "PMID": "28966590",
  "title": "TUBB2B Mutation in an Adult Patient with Myoclonus-Dystonia",
  "report": "A 31-year-old, right-handed, Caucasian woman of Northern European ancestry presented to the
  → Neurogenetics Clinic at the National Institutes of Health (Bethesda, MD, USA) for evaluation of
  → myoclonus-dystonia. Her parents were neurologically healthy; however, her sister had died at age
  → 30 years of genetically confirmed Friedreich ataxia. The patient herself did not carry a
  → pathologic FXN expansion. She was born at full-term via an uncomplicated vaginal delivery after an
  → uneventful pregnancy, weighing 3.35 kg. Her Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes were 8 and 9. She had
  → minor motor delays throughout infancy, such as not crawling until 10 months and a tremor with
  → minimal head tilt by 12 months. At this time, she was diagnosed with ..."
  "age": [[31.0, "year"]],
  "gender": "F",
  "summary": {
```

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Fig. 1. ELMTEX project experiments.

Table 1. Model performance comparison on our German dataset.

Models	ROUGE			BERTSc.	Entity-Level			
	R-1	R-2	R-L	F1	P	R	F1	
Naive	Llama-3.1-8B-Instr.	0.4956	0.37	0.4824	0.804	0.3716	0.3354	0.3525
	Llama-3.1-70B-Instr.	0.5191	0.3876	0.5055	0.8199	0.3779	0.3398	0.3578
	Llama-3.1-405B-Instr.	0.542	0.405	0.5285	0.832	0.3825	0.345	0.3627
Adv.+ICL	Llama-3.2-1B-Instr.	0.1745	0.1086	0.1688	0.6925	0.1839	0.1394	0.1585
	Llama-3.2-3B-Instr.	0.3255	0.2265	0.3132	0.7675	0.2919	0.2513	0.27
	Llama-3.1-8B-Instr.	0.5354	0.4228	0.5179	0.8409	0.4256	0.4145	0.4199
	Llama-3.1-70B-Instr.	0.6323	0.5127	0.6145	0.8625	0.4647	0.4595	0.462
	Llama-3.1-405B-Instr.	0.695	0.5787	0.6821	<u>0.9054</u>	0.5079	0.4914	0.4995
Fine-t.	Llama-3.2-1B-Instr.	0.6875	0.5693	0.6708	0.8853	0.4929	0.4875	0.4901
	Llama-3.2-3B-Instr.	<u>0.728</u>	<u>0.6159</u>	<u>0.7116</u>	0.9006	0.5182	0.5147	0.5164
	Llama-3.1-8B-Instr.	0.7338	0.6278	0.7186	0.9055	<u>0.5175</u>	<u>0.5119</u>	<u>0.5146</u>

```

"life_style": "Right-handed; Working full-time as a receptionist",
"family_history": "Sister died of genetically confirmed Friedreich ataxia; Parents neurologically
↪ healthy",
"social_history": "Caucasian; Northern European ancestry; Graduated from a high school that
↪ emphasized special education; Attended 1 year of community college",
"medical_surgical_history": "Minor motor delays in infancy; Diagnosed with mild cerebral palsy;
↪ Cervical dystonia at age 16; Intermittent upper body myoclonus; Generalized tonic-clonic seizure
↪ at age 30; Mild cognitive impairment",
"signs_symptoms": "Involuntary left head tilt; Left torticollis; Intermittent upper body myoclonus;
↪ Generalized tonic-clonic seizure; Mild cognitive impairment; Slight left laterocollis;
↪ Occasional myoclonic jerks; Low amplitude, high frequency postural tremor in left hand",
"comorbidities": "Attention deficit disorder",
"diagnostic_techniques_procedures": "EEG; Montreal Cognitive Assessment Test; Skin biopsy; Blood
↪ panels; Brain MRI; Genetic testing; Whole exome sequencing; Sanger sequencing",
"diagnosis": "Myoclonus-dystonia; Mild cerebral palsy; Cervical dystonia; Generalized tonic-clonic
↪ seizure; Neuronal migrational disorder; Isolated lissencephaly; Asymmetric temporal and parietal
↪ pachygyria; Enlarged and dysmorphic lateral ventricles; Dysmorphic basal ganglia; Dysmorphic
↪ hippocampi; Mild superior vermian cerebellar dysplasia; Bilateral genu valgum deformity; Left
↪ hip dysplasia; Dextroscoliosis with lumbar hyperlordosis",

```

```

"laboratory_values": "All blood panels within normal limits",
"pathology": "No evidence of a storage disorder in skin biopsy",
"pharmacological_therapy": "Trihexyphenidyl; Carbidopa/levodopa; Ritalin; Levetiracetam 750 mg 2
↪ times daily",
"interventional_therapy": "N/A",
"patient_outcome_assessment": "Seizure free on levetiracetam; Mild cognitive impairment; Static
↪ movement disorder",
"age": "31 year",
"gender": "Female"
}
}

```

C Naive Prompting

You are a helpful assistant. I will provide you a clinical report and I want you to extract several
↪ fields from it as strings and not lists.

If a field is not mentioned on the report provide the value "N/A", otherwise provide the extracted text.

JSON fields:

```

```json
{
 "life_style": "",
 "family_history": "",
 "social_history": "",
 "medical_surgical_history": "",
 "signs_symptoms": "",
 "comorbidities": "",
 "diagnostic_techniques_procedures": "",
 "diagnosis": "",
 "laboratory_values": "",
 "pathology": "",
 "pharmacological_therapy": "",
 "interventional_therapy": "",
 "patient_outcome_assessment": "",
 "age": "",
 "gender": ""
}
```

```

Clinical Report: [The patient report is appended here.]

D Advanced Prompting

TASK DESCRIPTION:

You are given a clinical report. Your task is to extract key information from the unstructured text and
↪ convert it into a structured JSON format. Each field should be populated with relevant details from
↪ the report, and if multiple pieces of information exist for a field, they should be separated by
↪ semicolons. If a particular field's information is not available in the report, use "N/A" (Not
↪ Available) for that field. Use the following structure for the output:

Field Descriptions:

- ****Life Style****: Extract information related to the patient's habits and daily activities, such as
 - ↳ smoking status, alcohol consumption, exercise, diet, occupation, and living environment.
- ****Family History****: Extract any relevant medical conditions or genetic disorders that run in the
 - ↳ patient's family, such as a history of heart disease, diabetes, or cancer.
- ****Social History****: Extract details about the patient's social background, including marital status,
 - ↳ support systems, substance use, and housing situation.
- ****Medical/Surgical History****: Extract any past medical conditions, chronic diseases, previous
 - ↳ surgeries, hospitalizations, or treatments the patient has undergone.
- ****Signs and Symptoms****: Extract the patient's current symptoms, their duration, and severity.
- ****Comorbidities****: Extract any other medical conditions the patient has that coexist with the primary
 - ↳ diagnosis, particularly those that may impact treatment.
- ****Diagnostic Techniques and Procedures****: Extract details of any diagnostic tests, imaging, or
 - ↳ procedures performed, such as X-rays, MRIs, blood tests, or biopsies.
- ****Diagnosis****: Extract the primary diagnosis as well as any secondary diagnoses or differential
 - ↳ diagnoses.
- ****Laboratory Values****: Extract specific laboratory test results, including values like blood counts,
 - ↳ electrolyte levels, or other relevant lab data.
- ****Pathology****: Extract findings from any pathological examinations, including biopsy results,
 - ↳ histopathology, or cytology.
- ****Pharmacological Therapy****: Extract details of any medications prescribed, including names, dosages,
 - ↳ frequency, and duration of treatment.
- ****Interventional Therapy****: Extract information on any surgical or non-surgical interventions, such as
 - ↳ procedures performed and their outcomes.
- ****Patient Outcome Assessment****: Extract the assessment of patient's current health status, functional
 - ↳ status, quality of life, and any follow-up plans.
- ****Age****: Extract the patient's age at the time of the report.
- ****Gender****: Extract the patient's gender as stated in the report.

Important Note:

- If any information is not available in the clinical report, use "N/A" (Not Available) for that field.

Instructions:

- Populate each field based on the information in the clinical report.
- Use semicolons to separate multiple entries within a single field.
- Use "N/A" (Not Available) for fields where information is not provided in the report.
- Ensure accuracy and completeness for each category.

Examples:

[In-Context Learning (ICL) examples are appended here.]

Clinical Report: [The patient report is appended here.]